

Remote Warfare: A Politically Expedient but Conceptually Flawed Construct

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This article argues that remote warfare is a politically expedient yet conceptually flawed construct, whose risk-averse rationale and deceptive 'cleanness' obscure its strategic limitations and ethical costs, ultimately undermining both military effectiveness and democratic integrity. It does this by exploring four key issues. First, it criticises its conceptual ambiguity. Second, it explores the relationship between the risk aversion mentality of Western decision-makers and their tendency to use remote warfare to achieve military goals, which could end up undermining underlying, 'big picture' strategic objectives. Third, it examines how the secrecy, asymmetric distribution of death, and unsubstantiated 'cleanness' inherent to remote warfare contribute to its use in Western democracies. Finally, this article delves into the extensive use of airstrikes – a means of remote warfare – to further explore the aforementioned relationship, since their relatively low risks lead to their indiscriminate usage regardless of context. Together, these points reveal that remote warfare functions less as a theoretical and strategic novelty than as a politically convenient alternative for decision-makers to externalise risk, obscure accountability, and pursue military objectives without addressing its underlying limitations.

INTRODUCTION

As the end of conscription in Western democracies led to transferring the risks of war to military professionals, the rise of 'remote warfare' (RW) shifts these same risks away from professional soldiers to the partner's or enemy's civilians and armed forces. This is how, in liberal democracies, "warfare has become primarily an exercise in risk-management" (Demmers and Gould, 2021, p. 38).

This article argues that RW is a politically expedient yet conceptually flawed construct, whose risk-averse rationale and deceptive 'cleanness' obscure its strategic limitations and ethical costs – ultimately undermining both military effectiveness and democratic integrity. It explores this claim through four connected issues: the conceptual limitations of RW, the strategic distortions produced by the decision-maker's risk-averse mentality that favours it, the ethical concerns masked by its secrecy and supposed 'cleanness', and the overreliance on airstrikes – which often become a default choice despite not always being the most effective or appropriate means of achieving military objectives.

First, the article engages with the challenges of defining RW and argues that its conceptualisation as a distinct category of warfare is counterproductive to the understanding of contemporary war. It does not intend to create a new definition of RW but to dissect the term by focusing on the idea of 'remoteness' and examining the limitations inherent to its conceptual ambiguity. Second, it outlines a positive correlation between Western leaders' risk aversion and the increased usage of RW and warns of the possible negative impact of this type of mentality on strategy. It does not propose a 'better alternative' for the use of force to decision-makers, but it explores the nature of this relationship by emphasising 'risk' as an inseparable notion of RW's theoretical and practical expressions. Third, it delves into the consequences of its secrecy and assumed 'cleanness'. Secrecy, like risk, constitutes a key element of RW, but it also presents a paradoxical challenge: it incentivises democratically-elected decision-makers to rely on RW due to its hermeticism and obturation of accountability, while also endangering the same democratic means that led to their election in the first place due to a distinctive lack of transparency. Finally, by briefly using the cases of the Gulf War, FARC, and ISIL, this article argues that the efficacy of airstrikes is highly dependent on the context yet seldom provides decisive results by themselves. Given the many existing expressions of RW, it is important to distinguish that airstrikes were chosen as a unit of analysis due to their extensive use in contemporary warfare, their profound strategic implications, and their inexorable link to remoteness. On that note, this article reflects on the strategic mistake of over-reliance on airstrikes

through a consideration of the reasoning behind their extensive use and the mixed results they have produced.

Through this analysis, the article claims that RW functions less as a distinct category of warfare and coherent strategic doctrine and more as an academic buzzword and means for decision-makers to externalise risk, obscure accountability, and pursue military objectives without fully confronting its consequences respectively. In situating this analysis within the broader literature, this article moves beyond the fragmented treatment of RW's individual elements to offer a unified, conceptually grounded critique. While scholars have examined RW from various angles, few have interrogated the concept itself as politically expedient yet fundamentally flawed in both theory and practice. In doing so, it offers a novel analytical framework that connects conceptual ambiguity with the strategic, ethical, and democratic costs of its use – reframing RW not as an illuminating concept or just as a policy choice, but as a symptom of redundant academic practice and deeper structural and political dynamics in contemporary Western democracies.

TO LIMIT IS TO UNDERSTAND: THE CHALLENGE OF DEFINING 'REMOTE WARFARE'

The conceptual singularity of RW is challenged by its overlapping boundaries with related concepts – 'proxy warfare', 'liquid warfare', 'hybrid warfare', etc. (Biegon and Watts, 2019, p.1). Although these concepts are not synonyms, the characteristics that should make them distinct categories of warfare overlap. Even without the existence of these other concepts, the notion of RW would still be disputed, given the lack of consensus regarding the elements that define it.

Biegon, Rauta, and Watts (2021, pp. 430–433) identify different approaches to understanding RW. Most adhere to either a 'techno-centric' or 'outcome-oriented' approach. While the former emphasises the impact of weapons and technology in behavioural, cultural, and legal terms, the latter studies a wider set of agents and practices. Both approaches share an interest in the remoteness of warfare, which, for the sake of this article, will be understood as the distance between the intervener's conventional forces and the frontline fighting. However, while 'techno-centric' perspectives focus, for example, on the use of drones for targeted killings, 'outcome-oriented' perspectives also consider the role of Special Forces (SF) and intelligence sharing (Biegon et al., 2021, p. 431).

It is important to distinguish that the remoteness of warfare is not understood in the same manner by all authors. For a concept that is supposed to be a distinct category of warfare, the lack of consensus regarding remoteness, the distinguishing quality of RW, is alarming. For most, it outlines a physical separation; for others, it refers to the distance between the public and the reality and costs of war (Adelman and Kieran, 2020, p. 9). Brunck (2020, p. 179) goes even further and proposes three different types of remoteness when discussing RW: 'spatial remoteness', 'cultural remoteness', and 'psychological remoteness'.

'Psychological remoteness', along with 'spatial remoteness', might be the most commonly explored type of remoteness in the literature. It refers to the depersonalisation that soldiers experience in the remote use of force – for example, piloting a UAV reduces the psychological cost of their actions by separating them from most risks and visible consequences (Asaro, 2009, p. 22; Heyns, 2016, pp. 354–355; Wagner, 2014, p. 1410). Nonetheless, it is important to note that there is no consensus regarding the correlation between RW and a reduction in the emotional cost of warfare for soldiers.

For instance, Fitzsimmons and Sangha (2013, p. 2) argue that remotely piloted aircraft operators experience similar combat stress levels to those experienced by regular military pilots, while Akhter and Shaw (2012, p. 1493) note that drone pilots develop PTSD faster than regular soldiers. Furthermore, Lee (2018, pp. 113–114) explains that it was the juxtaposition between the distant yet detailed, high-definition manner in which the RAF Reaper Force was exposed to violence and the banalities of day-to-day life which most affected them psychologically. Unlike the considerable distance between WWI pilots and their targets, the Reaper crews, even if on a different continent from their targets, witnessed everything at maximum camera resolution. Thus, the modern integration of high technology and remoteness in warfare both enhances its operational efficiency and intensifies the psychological toll on the soldiers involved.

Chapa (2021, p. 3) proposes the term 'phronetic distance', derived from Aristotle's notion of phronesis, meaning 'prudence' or 'practical wisdom'. It refers to the "relative distance between the battlefield and

the point of application of human judgement.” While exploring the psychological distance inherent to RW only sheds light on the relation between the effects of exercised violence and aircraft crews, ‘phronetic distance’ proposes the possibility of the application of human judgement from a closer epistemic distance despite the physical distance involved. To illustrate this better, Chapa (2021) utilises two different cases.

One such case is the former U.S. President Bill Clinton’s failed cruise missile strike against Osama bin Laden in 1998. The U.S. Navy fired a Tomahawk cruise missile from the Arabian Sea to Khost, Afghanistan, believing that bin Laden would be there. Notwithstanding, an apparently unrelated last-minute decision made bin Laden and his companions drive to Kabul instead. The U.S. Navy acted outside of the theatre of operations; once the launching was completed, the U.S. Navy officer in charge had no means of imposing his judgment since the cruise missile could not be recalled or redirected – and even if it could, the officer had no way of knowing that the received intelligence was mistaken. Thus, given the absence of the application of human judgment in response to the real-time dynamics of the changing situation, ‘phronetic distance’ was increased (Chapa, 2021, p. 4).

The other example that Chapa provides is regarding the U.S. 2011 raid in Abbottabad, Pakistan, where bin Laden was killed. This mission was characterised by three major setbacks: the forced landing and subsequent damage of the first helicopter to arrive; the second helicopter pilot’s decision to land outside bin Laden’s compound, forcing the SEALs to run into the latter from there; and the loss of communications between the raid force and Washington for approximately 25 minutes. However, since the raid force had the capability and authorisation to employ their judgment in response to the real-time challenges that might occur, a decision was made on the ground: to kill instead of capturing bin Laden. The mission was successful, and in this case, the decreased distance between the target and Special Forces authorised to make their own, real-time decisions led to a decrease in ‘phronetic distance’ (Chapa, 2021, p. 4).

In both examples, physical distance correlates with ‘phronetic distance’. In the first case, the point of application of human judgment is at the fingertips of the officer due to the location of the ship and target, and the technological constraints of the weapon. In the second case, the real-time application of human judgment was possible mainly because of Washington’s permission for the team to do so and the latter’s physical presence in the target area (Chapa, 2021, pp. 4–5). Nevertheless, the smaller physical distance between the agents and their targets – such as the raid force experienced in 2011 in contrast to the US Navy in 1998 – does not imply a smaller or non-existent ‘physical remoteness’, since Special Forces operations, such as the one in Abbottabad, are considered a means of RW (Biegon et al., 2021, pp. 430–433; Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 2). Thus, different means of RW imply different degrees of ‘phronetic distance’.

With a strong emphasis on ‘physical remoteness’, the Oxford Research Group (ORG) defines RW as a “term that describes approaches to combat that do not require the deployment of large numbers of your own ground troops” (Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 4). RW’s conceptual clarity is therefore suboptimal. The term can encompass many distinct military actions such as airstrikes, counterterrorism, security assistance, building partner capacities, and the aforementioned Special Forces operations, among others – all general military capabilities (Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 2). However, given that RW requires a distinction between conventional and non-conventional interventions, as well as determinations regarding where to draw the line between ‘light-footprint’ and large-scale deployments, the term presents challenges (McDonald, 2021, p. 531).

The lightness of the footprint of the forces engaging in RW also varies significantly. Unilaterally carrying out targeted killings abroad, performing ‘mentor’ roles in partner operations, or offering financial support to foreign governments or organisations imply disparate levels of engagement with RW. Nonetheless, there is a teleological distinction to be made: RW is always directed to the countering of an enemy; hence, supporting partners only falls under the category of RW when aimed at combating a third party (Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 3).

ORG’s definition also reveals that RW does not depend on remote weapons systems. Although these systems can increase the distance between operator and target, as in the case of drone strikes and cyberattacks, they can be used to support any kind of operation. Remote weapon systems are not a prerequisite for remoteness, as troops can be deployed on the battlefield as long as their number is limited, and ‘train, advise, and assist’ operations do not require the utilisation of this kind of systems.

Some authors also consider cyberattacks as part of RW. Ohlin supports this argument by highlighting how remoteness creates an inverse relationship between the attacker's risk and the target's vulnerability (Ohlin, 2017, pp. 27–28). If the end goal of RW is to grant immunity from risk to the operator while inflicting as much damage as possible to the enemy, then the use of cyber-weapons results in an even further detachment of the combatant from their target compared to drones. Although drone pilots might be far from the frontline, UAVs have a limited tactical range and still need a base in order to take off, refuel, and be repaired if necessary. Therefore, they depend on military infrastructure that can be found and targeted in an armed conflict. Thus, even if the pilot remains in his home country, part of the process – in this case, the deployment of the drone – remains foreign. Cyberattacks, on the other hand, can originate in any part of the globe and have almost no territorial constraints.

Given the difficulty of defining the concept, McDonald approaches RW not as a category of warfare, but as a complex relationship between a set of legitimacy problems and military capabilities. His interest lies in the “consequences of integrating military capabilities at a systems level in order to generate military effects” (McDonald, 2021, pp. 530–532). This perspective, although fairly complex, provides more conceptual rigour to RW in its precision. These kinds of attempts, no matter their traction within academia, provide greater clarity to a concept that, in its current broadness, hinders our understanding of contemporary warfare by explaining, through a new buzzword, things that have already been theorised.

The lack of conceptual clarity surrounding RW is not just a theoretical inconvenience; it is central to the broader problems this article identifies. This section has shown that remoteness, far from being a universally agreed-upon term, is deployed in inconsistent and often contradictory ways. The ambiguity around the concept allows for a flexible, often politically convenient framing of military actions that might otherwise demand public scrutiny or legal justification. In light of this, the next sections will show that this lack of definitional rigour facilitates the obscuring of civilian harm, the erosion of democratic oversight, and the overreliance on methods like airstrikes, all of which point back to the thesis that RW ultimately undermines both military effectiveness and democratic integrity.

THE EROSION OF STRATEGY AND OVERSIGHT: RISK-AVERSION, SECRECY, AND ‘CLEANNESS’

Voters in liberal democracies tend to disapprove of military action that results in casualties of their own forces (Chapa, 2021, p. 1). Indeed, in the case of the U.S., support of military intervention tends to decline as casualties – either real or expected – increase, even though the context, particularly the objectives and prospects for success, may result in an exception. Washington's involvement in World War II and Panama constitutes two exceptions to this tendency (Larson, 1996, pp. 7–10). RW, although not historically novel, became more common (Watson, 2020, p. 1) for Western powers during the Cold War and especially after the recent wars in Iraq and Afghanistan (Biegon and Watts, 2019, p. 3; Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 21).

The aforementioned conflicts had a deep impact on the foreign policies of Western democracies, resulting in a general crisis of public trust regarding the decision to deploy troops abroad (Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 7). It is in this sense that RW has become a getaway for politicians to decide over the use of military force while avoiding public criticism; it allows leaders to respond rapidly and in a limited, relatively cheap manner. This ‘moral hazard’ is rather simple to understand: given that RW provides policymakers with options that can substantially reduce the number of casualties amongst their own forces and hence cause little domestic political risk, there is a strong incentive for them to rely on its different means even if they violate International Humanitarian Law (Chapa, 2021, p. 1).

This represents a problem for strategic decision-making: *ceteris paribus*, there will always be an incentive to use RW even though it might not be the best option to deal with a certain threat. Karlshøj-Pedersen (2018) warns against this phenomenon by highlighting the “increasing risk that UKSF [UK's Special Forces] are used for political expediency above any assessment of whether they are the best tool for the job,” leading to an imbalance in funding that handicaps regular forces and that could have long-term consequences. Therefore, the danger of undermining ‘big picture’, strategic objectives by overestimating RW's suitability for most military scenarios due to short-term political gains looms over Western elites.

A 2013 leaked document of the British Ministry of Defence (MOD) explores the implications of the public's and state's current attitudes to risk regarding military operations. The study concludes that in order to

avoid public opposition (and considering that it is impossible to completely eliminate the dangers to military personnel during an armed conflict),

In 2015, the British government seemed to follow this advice, as Prime Minister David Cameron pledged to increase the investment in Special Forces and armed drones – a trend that continues to this day, especially regarding Special Forces (Chorley, 2015). The ‘National Security Strategy and Strategic Defence and Security Review’ (2015, p. 30) clearly evidenced this, as it announced that the current planned investments in Special Forces’ equipment were going to be more than doubled. Two years later, Prime Minister Theresa May pledged an additional £300 million to bring Special Forces “up to strength” while cutting the Royal Marines’ budget at the same time (Karlshoej-Pedersen, 2018). In summary, from 9/11 onwards, it has been a tendency for the UK’s Special Forces to expand considerably, even in times of contracting defence spending (Anglim, 2020), thus evidencing the growing interest of Western states in RW.

Along with the decision-makers’ ‘risk-averse’ mentality, RW has become more prevalent due to its asymmetrical distribution of death and suffering, the secrecy around its operations, and its deceitful portrayal as ‘clean’ (Demmers and Gould, 2021, p. 34). On the one hand, the asymmetrical distribution of death and suffering refers to the transferring of military risks from Western soldiers to the partner’s or enemy’s civilians and armed forces. On the other hand, secrecy around RW operations can be understood through the two following examples.

First, the UK MOD’s constant refusals to comment – either to the Parliament or press – on its use of Special Forces (Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 7). Second, the Netherlands’ withholding of information regarding the Hawija airstrike – resulting in around 70 civilian casualties (BBC, 2019) – for ‘security reasons’ (Utrecht University, 2023). This secrecy hinders democratic transparency and political deliberation on contemporary warfare, while also serving as an incentive for politicians to engage in RW. Moreover, RW also presents a challenge for the attribution of responsibility for the enforcement of International Humanitarian Law, since the processes behind remote operations are complex and hermetic. Split operations make this even harder; the control of UAVs, for example, can be transferred mid-flight and the infrastructure necessary for an operation might be located in a state that is not actually conducting it (McDonald, 2021, pp. 536–538).

The third aspect refers to the myth that RW is ‘cleaner’ than other types of warfare (Knowles and Watson, 2018, pp. 23–24) and follows the same logic as the media portrayals of Western airstrikes in Iraq and Kosovo during the 1990s. Even though these were conveyed to the public as dominated by the use of precision-guided munitions (PGM), this was not the case. While only 9% of the weapons dropped in Iraq and Kuwait were PGM, around 71% of the weapons released by NATO in Kosovo were unguided, causing many civilian casualties (Jordan, 2016, p. 277). More recently, between 2014 and 2018, the Royal Air Force dropped more than 3,700 missiles in its campaign against ISIL in Iraq and Syria. Estimates for the number of civilians killed in the battle for Mosul range from 1,000–10,000 (Knowles and Watson, 2018, p. 23). Thus, RW is not only not ‘clean’, but paradoxical: it makes Western democracies more prone to war as the “military violence executed is rendered so remote and sanitised, that it becomes uncared for, and even ceases to be defined as war” (Demmers and Gould, 2021, p. 34).

The asymmetrical distribution of death and suffering, secrecy, and deceitful portrayal of RW as ‘clean’ incentivise decision-makers to engage in it. As explained by Biegon and Watts (2021, p. 4) in the case of the U.S., as warfare has grown increasingly remote for the American public, the use of military force seems to face diminished constraints. These dynamics reveal how RW, far from being a purely operational shift, is intimately tied to a risk-averse mentality for decision-makers. The reduced visibility of war’s consequences, combined with the physical and psychological distance between publics and military action, enables decision-makers to bypass the democratic constraints traditionally placed on the use of force. Hence, RW is not merely a strategic tool but a politically expedient mechanism for externalising risk and deflecting accountability – precisely the kind of rationale that can undermine both effective military strategy and the integrity of democratic institutions. By masking violence behind a veil of secrecy and technological precision, RW creates the conditions for military engagement without public backlash, legal scrutiny, or strategic coherence. This last aspect will be further explored in the next section.

THE PRACTICAL LIMITATIONS OF AIRSTRIKES: THE CASES OF THE GULF WAR, FARC, AND ISIL

The enduring appeal of RW in Western democracies stems not only from its ability to minimise physical risks to national troops but also from its capacity to shield decision-makers from public scrutiny and ethical accountability. This is most evident in the heavy reliance on airstrikes, which are upheld as symbols of efficiency and cost-effectiveness. However, this dependency can result in strategic miscalculation, especially when airstrikes are employed as default solutions to intricate conflicts, rather than as context-sensitive tools within a comprehensive strategy.

The advantages of airpower are apparent: relatively risk-proof, greater reach, rapid deployability, and impermanence. Together, these characteristics can make airpower a key element of contemporary warfare. The Gulf War is one of the most illustrative examples, since ‘Operation Desert Storm’ resulted in the creation of a twenty-mile gap in Iraq’s air defence network that opened a corridor through which other American troops raced in (U.S. Army Center of Military History, n.d.).

Notwithstanding, the limitations of airstrikes – and therefore of some means of RW – become evident in General Powell’s and Lieutenant General Horner’s rejection of the initial Colonel Warden III’s ‘Instant Thunder’ plan. An air campaign that did not include an air-land joint operation, they argued, would not have been able to destroy the Iraqi army on the ground and therefore finish the war (Arkin, 1998). Their opposition led to the modification of the plan, which instead of solely consisting of strategic strikes in Iraq, also focused on the Iraqi forces in Kuwait and included a fourth phase in which a ground assault with air support would be carried out (Jordan, 2016, pp. 277).

Press (2001, pp. 7, 38) goes even further, arguing that airpower was neither sufficient nor necessary, since the Iraqi ground forces were completely outmatched by their American and British counterparts, and even with the absence of airstrikes, the coalition would have achieved victory. Indeed, while airstrikes can be crucial, they are hardly decisive by themselves, particularly when winning a war requires controlling territory by defeating the enemy’s army on the ground. The American military offensive in Iraq thus reveals the inadequacy of RW as a solution to every political problem that might require military action.

‘Fire from above’ cannot always deliver military results. Doane (2016) draws an analogy between the failures of targeting key revenue sources through airstrikes to combat FARC and ISIL. In order to financially hinder the former, the U.S. engaged in a series of aerial campaigns that sprayed herbicides to destroy coca-growing sites in Colombia. However, Washington’s aerial fumigation resulted only in a temporary setback for FARC, since the structural process behind the production of drugs continued. Moreover, it solidified the FARC’s narrative of a war on the peasantry by the Colombian government and resulted in coca growers asking for the FARC’s protection since the fumigation negatively affected their health and already dire material conditions.

Doane criticises how the U.S. planned targeted strikes to destroy ISIL’s pumping sites for the production of crude oil and the transport trucks destined to smuggle it. But as the coca fields were replanted, the pumping sites could be repaired, and an additional black market in repair parts and materials for the pumping stations could emerge and provide ISIL with an opportunity to tax illicit trade. Analogously to what happened with the coca growers in Colombia, American strikes on transport trucks might have provided a recruiting narrative to ISIL, since poor, civilian truckers, if not killed, dispossessed by the destruction of their means of livelihood, were unlikely to support their intervention.

Doane argues that the objectives of air campaigns – in this case, the financial crippling of ISIL – should have been pursued through different remote means. Integrated military operations with a ‘clear, hold, build’ logic would have been more suitable. In his own words: “Simply assaulting the group from the air or striking at their means of production is unlikely to yield a decisive result. Instead, counter-ISIL forces must prepare themselves for an extensive ground campaign to both cleave ISIL’s control of illicit funding sites and restore governmental control of those assets (Doane, 2016). In the same way that temporary tactical gains should never exacerbate the overall strategic problem (Watson, 2020, pp. 5–6), no means of RW, despite its short-term advantages, is suited to deal with every problem that could be remotely tackled.

Ultimately, this overdependence on RW reinforces the thesis that RW’s appeal lies less in its effectiveness than in its political convenience – namely, in facilitating action without adequately confronting the

limitations, responsibilities, or consequences such actions entail. The cases of the Gulf War and the campaigns against FARC and ISIL demonstrate how airstrikes, while attractive alternatives, often fall short when deployed as a stand-alone solution. In the Gulf War, initial plans that centred exclusively on airpower were quickly revised due to concerns that they could not deliver decisive outcomes without ground support. This illustrates that even in conventional conflicts, airstrikes alone are rarely sufficient to secure strategic goals. Similarly, in the campaigns against FARC and ISIL, remote strikes aimed at dismantling key infrastructure proved to be both temporary and counterproductive, failing to address the structural conditions that sustained these organisations. In some cases, they even reinforced enemy narratives and alienated local populations. These examples underscore that RW's apparent efficiency can conceal its inability to produce durable outcomes, particularly when its use is shaped more by the desire to avoid domestic political costs than by careful strategic planning. As such, the overreliance on airstrikes exemplifies the broader pattern identified in this article: the substitution of political expediency for strategic coherence, its consequent operational overreach, and the externalisation of risk in ways that ultimately undermine both military effectiveness and democratic accountability.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, this article has demonstrated that RW is a politically expedient, yet conceptually flawed construct incentivised by an underlying risk-averse logic and deceptive assumption of 'cleanness' that mask its strategic and ethical shortcomings, diminishing both military effectiveness and democratic integrity. The lack of precise conceptual boundaries and academic consensus regarding 'remoteness' results in the use of RW as an unclear way of distinguishing a new category of warfare that is neither distinct nor new. Approaches like McDonald's (2021), both more original and theoretically robust, help to shed light on a diverging literature.

On the other hand, there is a relationship between the risk aversion mentality of Western decision-makers and their tendency to use RW as a means to achieve military goals, which could end up undermining 'big picture' strategic objectives. Secrecy, the asymmetric distribution of death, and the unsubstantiated 'cleanness' of RW all contribute to this trend, leading to a lack of democratic transparency, complicating the enforcement of International Humanitarian Law, and obscuring civilian casualties. Airstrikes also show the dangers of the aforementioned relationship, since their relatively low risk results in their indiscriminate usage regardless of the context, even if it is against conventional forces as originally planned by Colonel Warden III in Iraq, or either 'spider' or 'starfish' unconventional organisations abroad. If warfare has become primarily an exercise in risk management, then it stands to reason that RW manifests as one of its most prevalent expressions.

This article contributes to the growing literature on RW by offering a cohesive critique that connects these disparate issues under a single thesis. In doing so, it moves beyond narrow debates to reframe RW as a symptom of deeper political and structural tendencies in contemporary Western democracies. In essence, it is a means of externalising violence while internalising legitimacy. Thus, this article interrogates the assumptions and incentives that make it so politically attractive – and so strategically and ethically fraught. Furthermore, it challenges the tendency to analyse RW in terms of its isolated elements. Understanding RW demands attention to the manner in which risk is managed, violence is obscured, and accountability is avoided. By stressing this intersection, the article not only clarifies why RW is both conceptually and practically problematic, but also why rethinking it is fundamental to restoring strategic cohesion and democratic control in contemporary warfare and military decision-making

Finally, further research should explore how the concept of remoteness operates in different parts of the world and political systems, particularly in non-Western and authoritarian contexts where the dynamics of legitimacy, risk, and accountability may differ. Empirical studies comparing how various states understand and implement RW could also shed light on the understanding of remoteness. Additionally, greater theoretical engagement is needed to unravel the intersections between RW and other related concepts such as hybrid and liquid warfare, since it is only by interrogating the blurry boundaries of RW that the field can further develop its understanding of contemporary warfare.

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